

Internal Dynamics of Conflict in Afghanistan: An Assessment

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Abstract

There is abundance of literature available on the external sources of conflict in Afghanistan and the latter is considered as gateway and pawn of great powers' rivalries. This paper, however, is focused on the internal dynamics and sources of conflict in Afghanistan. These include the triangular sources i.e. ethnic diversity, dysfunctional governance system, and the return of warlords and militia commanders in Afghan society. In post-US Afghanistan, these three dynamics might further exacerbate the race for powers in Kabul and can lead to another forthcoming civil war. These parameters are intervening and resulted in the perpetual existing conflict which might be continued in the foreseeable future. The central theme of this paper is to study, investigate, and analyze these three intervening factors as a source of continued conflicts. Major questions to be investigated are: what are the internal sources of conflicts in Afghanistan? What are the reasons for perpetual conflicts and continued strife in Afghanistan?

Introduction

South Asian security is a key to the stability and instability of Afghanistan. If the state of Afghanistan is internally fractious and fragmented, the spillover effects towards its neighbors are likely in the future. It is often considered in the literature that Afghanistan is a gateway to conquests and great powers politics. However, the legacy of war, ethnic and linguistic differences, and struggle of power lead to the failure of the Afghan state and society (Zartman, et al, 2005: 223). The complex linguistic, ethnic, and cultural dependence and similarity all contributed to the dominion effects of the internal dynamics of Afghanistan's neighbours, particularly Pakistan. The continued conflicts and strife in Afghanistan are due to the diverse ethnic landscape, dysfunctional governance system, and the powers that reside with regional warlords and militia commanders.

Internal dynamics, structure, and complexities of any state are essential characteristics while examining the perpetual conflicts and instability. It is agreed that multi-ethnic and heterogeneous composite states are more likely to be in a state of conflicts and ethnic tension (Zartman et al, 2005: 223). What constitutes elite political culture that is based on the promotion of ethnic violence is the state's lack of coercive power which suppresses ethnic-based violence (Carment, 1998: 82). In the case of Afghanistan, its political and military history portray that the civil and internal conflicts were the main dynamics exploited by the political elites, warlords, and local autonomous and powerful leaders. This problem further intensified when the US invaded Afghanistan with aims at rooting out Al-Qaida and Taliban elements. However, the US after decades failed to end the perpetual violence and internal strife, and dysfunction of the Afghan state and government. The US-led operation in Afghanistan led to state failure, an increase in ethnic violence dividend political landscape of the Afghan states (Stein, 2001: 17).

For both US and the international communities as national builders, the dilemma has remained as putting together the major ethnic groups in Afghanistan with Pashtuns as dominant and assuring that it will not victimize other ethnic groups. Initially, the US did not follow reaching out to the Pashtuns in Afghanistan because the Northern Alliance was their major ally against the Taliban. Thus, the US deliberately politicized the ethnic and religious groups in Afghanistan and this is still proving to be a major obstacle in the peace process and political harmony. This problem can be summed up that the current political distrust has roots in the lack of moderate Pashtuns leadership who unite all the Afghan nationals into one identity and law (Ollapally, 2008: 58).

Afghanistan: Internal Dynamics of the perpetual Conflicts

Diagram.1.0. Internal Cycle of Afghan Conflicts

Ethnic Division as a Source of Conflict in Afghanistan

It is important to assess the internal structure of Afghanistan while discussing the violent and enduring conflicts for decades. It is more common as mentioned by 35 that a diverse ethnic composition of society often leads to ethnic violence and fragmentation of the state. This further complicates the internal structure while elite and warlords exploit these fault lines for their own interests. Thus, the connection between ethnicity, violence, elite's exploitation and warlords can't be ignored while analysing the internal structure of the Afghan state which has proven to perpetual conflicts and strife.

The ethnic division and fault lines have been witnessed throughout the political history of Afghanistan. This led to various internal conflicts, an uprising against government, interethnic cleansing and civil wars. Along with the ethnic divide, there is a religious divide based on sectarianism particularly from the Sunni Taliban against the Shia's population of Afghanistan. Apart from the above-mentioned aspects, the historical, cultural diversity, ethnic and linguistic differences have impacted the political stability of Afghanistan. After the downfall of the Najibullah regime in 1992, Afghanistan witnessed civil war, constant turmoil and alliance forming within ethnic groups which lead to the Afghan society based on the ethnic and linguistic divide. This result in the formation of local order and areas of influence lead by warlords and militia commanders. These local warlords committed atrocities against ethnic groups as a historical grievance and violate basic human rights. With the emergence of the Taliban on the screen, they violate and reinforced ethnic divisions between Pashtuns and Hazara. The Hazara ethnic groups strongly opposed the Taliban strict adherence to Sharia Law.

These divisions and ethnic splits continued after the fall of the Taliban in Afghanistan. The post-Taliban governments of Hamid Karzai and Ashraf Ghani also strived to ease the ethnic division and rivalry, however, just like historical patterns and amity between ethnic groups the division and clash of interests are continued (Clement, 2003: 16). The historical pattern and analogy suggest that ethnic division and rivalry is the major stumbling block to the unified and harmonious Afghan society.

What constitutes the violence based cultures and perpetual conflicts based on the ethnic line are the state coercive power when trying to suppress the mounting challenges and enmity based on ethnicity and groups identity lead to further violence in any state (Carment and James, 1998: 63). It is true in the context of Afghanistan civil conflict and continued ethnic tension as the political elite and dominate the group of the government uses coercive power to suppress ethnic-based challenges result in further split and antagonism among ethnic groups and lead to divide and eternally fractious societal structure. The Afghan state lacks the capacity to deal with the enduring challenges ranging from administrative to economic, social and political aspects (Stein, 2001: 18). It should be noted that apart from heterogeneity and complex ethnic structure, economic backwardness, social divisions and lack of modernization are also part and provide lucid analysis for an ethnic problem in Afghanistan.

It would be wrong to isolate ethnic conflicts from domestic affairs and has a profound effect on the internal structure of the state. Few ethnic conflicts are bound to the internal and domestic aspects of the state while the majority of the ethnic strife has external links (Montalvo and Marta, 2005: 297). In the context of Afghanistan, this domestic pattern of internal conflict has no exemption from the external ethnic environment. Furthermore,

the constant ethnic struggle for power in Afghanistan, make it internally fragmented with perpetual violence and civil wars which led to external intervention and influences.

This ethnic division also prompts Afghanistan's neighbour's states to promote and protect their interests by meddling and intervening in the internal aspects of Afghanistan. The ethnic rivalry in Afghanistan is coloured through political lines and shapes (Barfield, 2011: 32). This cycle of ethnic conflicts shape and often change the internal security structure and dynamics of the Afghanistan state. One can argue that if there is no external ethnic interference and political motivations, the Afghan ethnic landscape and harmony would not be as fractious as witnessed for decades.

In these scenarios, the state failed to provide and secure basic fundamental rights, protection against violence, economic well-being and a sound justice and legal system (Doyle and Sambanis, 2000: 773). The same is true and witnessed from the Afghan state, where economic problems, protracted violence and the state's lack of control led to internal fragmentation and civil wars. All the above-mentioned aspects affect and spark ethnic hostility.

Dysfunctional Governance

Functional and good governance is the first and foremost variable for maintaining security and fostering economic development in any state. According to the National Directorate of Security, to counter the Taliban control and propaganda, it is required that local administrative and governance must be stable, sound and functioning. There must be honest and capable leadership for the effective functioning of these institutions. The major sources which undermined the effectiveness of good governance in Afghanistan are the warlords, ethnic division and tribal and militia commanders at local levels (Saleh, 2006: 10).

In the case of Afghanistan, for example, the post 9/11 government focused on the rehabilitation and economic uplift of the Afghan state but failed to achieve the favour of the main ethnic groups. The government of Hamid Karzai and Ashraf Ghani tried their best to reach out to solve the problems that are common masses facing. But the truth is that these governments lack legitimacy and popular support from the major chunk of the Afghan population. These rebuilding efforts will take decades and the key is the restoration of democracy and public faith in the government and the system. This further needs the restoration of peace, infrastructural and educational systems, political reach and control up to rural areas and strengthen the local governance system.

The major dilemma for post-Bonn governments in Afghanistan was lost institutional legitimacy. This is due to the individual pattern and behaviour. 154. In Afghanistan, democratic institutions have lost legitimacy and public confidence. At both national and subnational level of governance, corruption has risen significantly based on patronage by recruiting friends, family members, party and ethnic-based affiliations have ruined the efficiency (Nijat, 2014: 39). High post designated for technical know-how has been filled on patronage and favouritism. The political efficiency of government institutions at subnational levels has been far more perverted. Moreover, there is a lack of control and check over the local administration over corruption and misuse of powers. The dysfunctional justice system is one of the key reasons due to which corruption is prevailing at both national and sub-national levels in Afghanistan (Stone, et al, 2005: 45).

Post-Doha Afghanistan is undergoing major changes and challenges ahead. There is a lot of optimism and hope for the restoration of peace, stability and democracy in Afghanistan. The US and the Taliban deal is hope in this direction as the US forces will withdraw within fourteen months, but the process of peace and stability is ahead. The current political landscape of Afghanistan is still divided into ethnic and political lines. The arranging of separate oath-taking ceremonies by both presidential candidates Ashraf Ghani and Abdullah Abdullah is the witness of ethnic-based divergence. It seems that it will be too difficult for the coalition government in Kabul to win the hearts and minds of the common Afghan people against the looming threats of the Taliban and will struggle for legitimacy and support from a majority of the population. The state rebuilding will be the fewest concern if the continued distrust and disagreements prevail among political leaderships in Afghanistan.

Moreover, the lack of public trust and service delivery to the common masses at both national and subnational levels derogated public support against insurgency. The Taliban use this rhetoric's and faultiness of the Afghan states with promises to make them functional. The Taliban elements are in constant propaganda to fill the vacuum left by the Afghan state (Brown and Clements, 2009: 42).

There is still a lot of optimism about the political, economic and security aspects in Afghanistan that peace, prosperity will come to the war-ravaged country. The Presidential deal between Ashraf Ghani and Abdullah Abdullah as chief executive is the light in this direction and zigzag process for peace. However, the siding of the current Afghan government in a peace deal with the Taliban and the shifting of power in their favour marked the future gloomy. Thus, the return of the Taliban to power will antagonize inter-Afghan civil war and the confrontations in the future between the Taliban and Northern Alliance are likely. Moreover, once the US forces leave, will result in widespread chaos and security degradation in Afghanistan. The Afghan national security forces are in fragile condition mainly based on the US and other donor's aid and assistance will sharply decline and demoralized.

The internal dynamics in Afghanistan are in constant flux as the return of former warlords and militia commanders raced for government stakes and slots during President Ghani period. The looming threat of

another civil war is seen in Kabul. Most of the segments of the Afghan population especially Pashtuns consider the government of Ghani and puppet of the western power and absolutely corrupt and incompetent to deal with their miseries and problems. As along with the US forces the Afghan security forces violate the local cultural values during the anti-insurgents campaigns which result in widespread distrust and hate against their government. At local and district levels, distrust and hostility are on the rise and many tribes put their alliance in the hand of the Taliban to support their struggle against ousting the current government.

Warlords and Militia Commanders

Warlords and militia commanders are the legacy of war in Afghanistan. Powerful regional warlords and regionalism have been part of Afghan political culture and landscape for decades (Jones, 2002: 28). Since the 2004 presidential elections which established a democratic government in Afghanistan, however, with weak central control and administrative reach. Since 2004, the local warlords and militia commanders pose a direct threat to the central government in Kabul. "I am giving up warlordism; I am going to Kabul to be a minister (Chayes, 2006: p. 148)". Furthermore, the return of these warlords also halted the US and Afghan governments counterinsurgency campaigns.

Malejacq (2009) noted that the "term warlords often used and synonym of brutality, racketeering and suffering of civil communities in political and normative ways." Warlords are also considered as political magnets whose legitimacy and power make war more destructive and prolong. These actors play important roles in public, political and economic aspects and influence. The government also used warlords in the areas where they have access and control of political, economic and security interests and influences. In the case of Afghanistan and US interests, the role of warlords cannot be ignored. From the very beginning since the US lead operation against the Taliban, the US and Afghan governments used them to advance their influences and expel external elements, Taliban and Al-Qaida. The US approach of state-building in Afghanistan is questionable as both the US and the Afghan government supported the role of warlords in the political and security process (Malejacq, 2009: 32).

Afghanistan's social and ethnic landscape consists of fourteen ethnicities that on many occasions seem competing for their interests. The major divide is between the Pashtuns and Tajiks ethnic groups (Riedel, 2017: 4). Currently, the President of Afghanistan Ashraf Ghani is from the Pashtuns tribe while his Chief executive Abdullah Abdullah is from Tajik ethnicity who often consider a political rival. This ethnic division forces major regional figures and powerful warlords to align themselves with the government with the aim to strengthen their power, interests and avoid marginalization by the central government. The alignment of the powerful figure and warlords with their ethnicity makes them stronger, and their stakes in the political and security aspects can't be ignored (The Economist, 2017).

Currently, for the government of Ashraf Ghani, the role and position of warlords are important in the context of their influence and regional control. These warlords are so powerful that the central government negotiates with them with the aim to achieve their favour. For example, Atta Muhammad Noor, who is a powerful Tajik figure in the Balkh province, is considered a close ally of Abdullah Abdullah and President Ghani negotiated with him and assigns the post of the governorship of Balkh (The Economist, 2016). Initially, Noor Muhammad did not support and recognized the government of Ashraf Ghani; however, later on in 2017 after acquiring the position of governor, he put his weight behind Ghani's government (Tolo News, 2017).

According to the Afghan National Security Council's National Threat Assessments, the warlords and their militia armed groups are the direct threat to Afghanistan's national security and a major obstacle to the government for territorial and administrative reach and rebuilding of the war turned infrastructure. The governance, socio-economic and security goals can't be achieved with the existence of warlords (Afghan Ministry of Defence, 2005: 3).

Jalali (2006: 8) noted that for decades Afghanistan lacked a strong and central government. He further noted that the US-Afghan government relied on the warlords and this resulted in the empowerment of militia commanders and regional leaders as compared to the central government. When the US started Operational Enduring Freedom against the Taliban they strengthened the Northern alliance to overthrow the Taliban government. The US support to the Northern Alliance continued long as the Taliban insurgency continued. This support worked as a double-edged sword by combating the Taliban elements but also empowered and increased the powers of the local warlords and militia commanders. The Afghan government tried to integrate and reduce the influence of warlords by offering governmental posts and perks but their strength continued (Roe, 2005: 20). This makes the local administrative system dysfunctional and regional commanders and warlords become stronger equipped with arms supplied by the US.

Both governments of President Hamid Karzai and Ashraf Ghani took reconciliatory approaches towards several warlords and militia commanders pulling them to bring under the political architecture of the state and offered them governmental and administrative positions what Malejacq termed as "warlords turning as bureaucrats." This bargaining process of the Afghan government was based on the perception that it will strengthen their authority at the periphery and far-flung areas. It was President Karzai and Ashraf Ghani decisions to bring the

warlords and militia commanders into Kabul political and administrative apparatus with the aim that they will overthrow violence and will establish their control against the Taliban in peripheries of the Afghan state. However, both did not persuade the warlords to shun off violence and arms in order to achieve peace and prosperity. Furthermore, the inclusion in the government also put them in favourable positions to constitute and start structural and continued violence (Mukhopadhyay, 2011: 78).

The internal security situation in Afghanistan further deteriorated because of the rise of opium cultivation and their alleged revenues and finance used for arms and alieving insurgency. It should be noted that opium cultivation was drastically reduced during the Taliban regime and again boosted after the toppling of the Taliban government by the US. It is a fact that opium and poppy cultivation is part of many Afghans who live below the poverty level.

It should be noted that armed conflicts, continued insurgency and civil wars are often fuel by narcotic trade and their smuggling. If there is ongoing arm conflict, the parties involved used the drugs as a source for finance and continued their activity (Cornell, 2005: 42). The same is true in the context of Afghanistan, where the insurgents, militia groups and warlords used drugs and poppy cultivation as a source for revenues and finance to continue their insurgency and conflicts. Thus, there are direct relations between illicit drugs and armed conflict and insurgency. For the forthcoming Afghan government or the existing government, the war against drugs is another test and task; this involves the providence of an alternative source of income and facilitation to the rural population of Afghanistan.

The way forward

It is significant to study, analyse and understand the internal source of conflicts and continued insurgency in Afghanistan. Internally, the state and society of Afghanistan are fragmented, fractious and divided on ethnic, cultural and to the minor extent of religious lines. It is the inability of the Afghan governments to unite different cultural and ethnic groups in one national umbrella in order to end the perpetual conflict. There are some recommendations made by the Afghan government and the US to reconsider the internal dynamics and source of conflicts with the intention to achieve peace and prosperity in Afghanistan. These include:

All major powers and particularly the US should look and monitor even after the withdrawal the rivalry between major ethnic groups, militia commanders, warlords and the emerging elements of ISIS in Afghanistan. The logic of international cooperation and support is vital to halt the return of chaos into the decade's conflict-ridden Afghanistan.

The Afghan government should try to integrate different ethnic and rebels groups in one statehood and should consider their due rights and share in the government circles. It is common that when a specific group and ethnic community are marginalized by the government led to an arms struggle and insurgency to achieve their goals. In this sense, many groups used and currently using violence as a tool to achieve their agendas and due share in the government. Therefore, it should be the prime motive of the government in Kabul to keep these groups under uniting umbrella because undoing so will lead to further bloodshed, chaos and civil wars.

The US approach to established democratic government and institutions in Afghanistan is questionable in the context of the latter. The Afghan society is based on religious conservatism, ethnic divide and tribal and rural culture which hinder the western pattern of democracy (Chayes, 2006: 87). To establish democracy, all major and regional powers should facilitate the pre-conditions for ideal democracy in Afghanistan which includes a stable internal security environment, education and effective local governance, economic development and power-sharing at the central level. All these dynamics should be addressed in Afghanistan for proper democratic institution-building (Etzioni, 2004: 8).

All major ethnic groups and stakeholders and their due share in the central government may harmonize the internal fictions in Afghanistan. But it seems very difficult in the current existing internal political and security environment in Afghanistan. However, a broad-based Afghan government that represent all the relevant stakeholders is the only way out.

On governance notice and efficiency, it is necessary that the national and subnational government institutions should be made coherent, free of patronage and corruption. This will not only enhance public perception about politics and government institutions and also solve the miseries of the common people.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the US-led operation Enduring Freedom was aimed to turn down the enduring violence and extremism in Afghanistan badly failed because a military solution to the Afghan cold rum is no more viable. The US also failed to grasp the internal and external complexities of the Afghanistan state in dealing with ending conflict, extremism and the Taliban elements in Afghanistan. What links missed is the institutional governance and structure of the Afghan government which would remedy the problem that the common masses facing along with the economic and educational aspects to foster peace and prosperity in Afghanistan.

For this purpose, the preconditions ranging from stable, strong and legitimate government which represent all ethnic sections, security forces and socio-economic links that lack the current government of Ashraf Ghani. These goals are the preconditions for achieving peace and prosperity in Afghanistan currently and even beyond

in the future. The current scenario, in Afghanistan and the historical experiences portray the pessimistic future of Afghanistan. Because the historical record suggests that the Afghan government lack central control over provinces and the local politics are headed by warlords and influential militia commanders based on ethnic and sectarian lines. Thus, political and economic stabilization in Afghanistan links with cultural, ethnic and religious lines and parameters.

The emerging political and security situation of Afghanistan is more cumbersome, confictions and fractions are likely if seen in the context of current internal parameters. The three major intervening variables or cycles i.e. ethnic, security and political dysfunctional governance make peace and rebuilding of the Afghan state less likely in the future. The central theme of the overall paper is thus, indicating that the three major factors are intervening and affecting peace and prosperity in Afghanistan. By looking only at the external and foreign interventions in Afghanistan are not comprehend the pattern of conflict. All efforts of the regional stakes can be meaningless if the continued internal fractions in Afghanistan are not addressed. For this purpose, the US and all regional powers should work on the internal conflicts in Afghanistan to foster governance and nation-building. The rhetoric that Afghanistan is a post-conflict state is based on myth as the latter is an active war state with continued internal wars and struggle for powers. Therefore, the efforts need to harmonize the internal war and power struggle in order to achieve durable solutions, peace and prosperity.

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